

Appendix A: Log of the observations

The log of the observations used for the ULLYSES targets in N11 B analyzed in this work is listed in Table A.1 and Table A.2.

Appendix B: Photometry

The photometric values used to construct the SEDs of the analyzed stars in N11 B are listed in Table B.1.

Appendix C: PoWR models

The PoWR models for the analyzed stars in N11 B is shown in Fig. C.1 to Fig. C.14. The SED and photometric magnitudes are shown in the first panel of each Figure. UV and optical spectra (blue line) are shown normalized to the continuum model. Balmer lines and the most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, are shown separately in comparison with the model. The models for the three additional objects are shown in Fig. C.15 to Fig. C.20.

Appendix D: Check for binarity

The search for binarity features in the analyzed stars in N11 B is shown in Fig. D.1 to Fig. D.6.

Appendix E: Additional O-type stars of different sub-type in LMC

The physical parameters obtained with PoWR for three additional O-type stars of different sub-types in LMC are reported in Table E.1. Their chemical abundances and the stellar parameters derived with BONNSAI are listed in Table E.2 and Table E.3, respectively.

Appendix F: Comments on the O-type stars analyzed in this work

Next, we will briefly comment on each of the analyzed objects and compare our results with previously reported parameters for some of our stars.

PGMW 3053. a.k.a. N11 18, is a mid O-type bright giant star initially classified as O5.5 I-III(f) by Parker et al. (1992), later reclassified as O6 II(f+) by Walborn et al. (1995); Evans et al. (2006); Vink et al. (2023), and revised as O6.5 II(f) by PAC (priv. comm.). With GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra, we note that the He II $\lambda 4686$ line profile is variable within a time window of 1 day (see Fig. D.5). Evans et al. (2006, in their Tab.6) mentioned a possible " v_{rad} or wind variability". However, the difference in strength of this line due to this variability is rather small and does not have a significant impact in the determined $\dot{M}$. There are no other available epochs of observations to check for additional periods of probable variability for this line. The rest of the He lines observed at different time intervals do not vary over periods ranging from days to months and do not exhibit a double-peak profile. Thus, according to our analysis, no evidence of binarity was found in this object. No contamination from additional sources was found by inspecting *HST*/WFPC2 images in filters F656N and F502N.

Previously, Evans et al. (2006, in their Fig. 12) adopted a temperature for this star based on its spectral type and metallicity. Later, Martins et al. (2024) reported $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.67$, $T_{\star} = 37$ kK and $\log g = 3.6$. Here we determined lower values:

$\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.55$, $T_{\star} = 34.7$ kK, and $\log g = 3.45$. We also report $\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.1$. We find that nitrogen is enriched by a factor of 7, having the highest N enrichment in our sample, and by 2 in carbon. Silicon on the other hand, has to be reduced by 4 to match the Si IV $\lambda 4088.9$ line, although not the Si IV $\lambda 4116.1$ in emission. We were not able to reproduce the mentioned Si IV lines when they are in emission (for any of the stars) with our PoWR modeling. We also note that the modeled N III $\lambda 4634.1$, $\lambda 4640.6$ lines in emission are not strong enough to reproduce the observed features (see Sec. 4.4 for discussion).

The $v \sin i$ parameter is determined from the metal line in absorption N III $\lambda 4515$ (with EW= 50 mÅ and SNR= 200, in the neighboring continuum), resulting in $v \sin i = 88$ km s⁻¹, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 15$ km s⁻¹. Using Si IV (EW= 70 mÅ; SNR= 180) one obtains $v \sin i = 68$ km s⁻¹, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 66$ km s⁻¹. We note a discrepancy between the values obtained from different metal lines. For this star, we select the $v \sin i$ obtained from the N III $\lambda 4515$, given the consistency of the values obtained by the FT and GOF methods (see Fig. 3).

The replicated observables with BONNSAI were: $T_{\star} = 34.7$ kK, $\log g = 3.54$, $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.6$, and $v \sin i = 90$ km s⁻¹. BONNSAI assumes a $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) \sim 0.05$ dex and $\log g = 0.1$ dex higher than the introduced values. We remark these differences given the predicted M_{ev} is higher than the determined M_{spec} .

Nazé et al. (2014) reported an upper limit for its X-ray luminosity of $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) < -7.1$. We include X-rays to reproduce certain features in the UV, the N V $\lambda 1238.8$, $\lambda 1242.8$ and the O VI $\lambda 1031.9$, $\lambda 1037.6$. Given that the upper limit previously reported for the $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}})$ ratio is practically the same value we obtained, we thoroughly explored the set of three free parameters that could give us an even lower ratio (x_{fill} , T_X , and r_{min}). However, if T_X is reduced by 0.1 MK, then the N V is weaker than the observation, so this option was discarded. On the other hand, by increasing x_{fill} or r_{min} , then the O VI $\lambda 1031.9$, $\lambda 1037.6$ become more intense or broader than the observed lines. A similar exercise was done for the rest of the analyzed stars. Here we report a ratio of $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) = -7.0$.

PGMW 3058. a.k.a. N11 60, is an early O dwarf star, classified as O3 V((f*)) by Walborn et al. (2004), and revised without change by PAC (priv. comm.). According to our analysis of the GIRAFFE spectra, there is no evidence of binarity. Previously, Mokiem et al. (2007a) determined $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.57$, $T_{\star} = 45.7$ kK, $\log g = 3.92$ and $\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.28$. Based on recent Gaia DR3 photometry (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2016, 2023), we obtain $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.35$, which is a lower value by 0.2 dex. Also our temperature is lower by 6 kK ($T_{\star} = 40$ kK), and we get half the mass-loss rate value ($\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.5$). The replicated observables with BONNSAI were: $T_{\star} = 39.2$ kK, $\log g = 3.9$, $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.38$, and $v \sin i = 60$ km s⁻¹. BONNSAI assumes a slightly lower $T_{\star}$, and higher values for $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot})$ and $\log g$, affecting the obtained M_{ev} , which is higher than M_{spec} . We find that this object is enriched in N by a factor of 3. C is has to be reduced by 50, O by 5, and Si by 4.

The $v \sin i$ is determined from the metal line in absorption N V $\lambda 4603.8$ (EW= 190 mÅ; SNR= 230), resulting in $v \sin i = 66$ km s⁻¹, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 80$ km s⁻¹. N V $\lambda 4619.9$ is weaker (EW= 110 mÅ; SNR= 230). From this line we obtain $v \sin i = 81$ km s⁻¹, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 35$ km s⁻¹. We did not consider C IV $\lambda 5801$ or C IV $\lambda 5811$ given they are observed in emission. Neither other weaker lines, like the O III $\lambda 5592.3$.

For this star, Nazé et al. (2014) reported $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) < -7.05$. We report $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) = -7.5$, a value below the upper

Table A.1. Log of the spectroscopic observations used for the analysis of the ULLYSES targets in N11 B.

Object Name (1)	Telescope (2)	Instrument (3)	ID (4)	λ (Å) (5)	R (6)	Date (yy/mm/dd) (7)	Exp. t. (s) (8)	SNR (9)	P.I. (10)	slitsize / PA (arcsec / deg) (11)
PGMW 3053	<i>FUSE</i>	<i>FUSEMDRS</i>	FUV	904–1189	15000–20000	2001/11/14	8377		Roman-Duval, J.	4 × 20
	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G130M</i>	FUV	1131–1428	12000–16000	2020/08/08	475		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G160M</i>	FUV	1418–1790	13000–20000	2020/08/08	699		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1a	3849–4048	22000	2003/12/05	6825	191	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1b	3849–4048	22000	2003/10/16	6825	178	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2a	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/06	6825	134	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2b	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/05	6825	136	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3a	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	133	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3b	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	136	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	261	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	211	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5a	4537–4761	23000	2003/12/08	6825	259	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5b	4537–4761	23000	2003/12/07	6825	236	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6a	6300–6690	17000	2003/11/12	6825	265	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6b	6300–6690	17000	2003/10/12	6825	223	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2020/12/16	750	185	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –170
<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2020/12/16	820	121	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –170	
PGMW 3058	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G130M</i>	FUV	1131–1428	12000–16000	2021/04/11	2066		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G160M</i>	FUV	1419–1790	13000–20000	2021/04/11	1996		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1a	3849–4048	22000	2003/12/05	6825	102	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1b	3849–4048	22000	2003/10/16	6825	94	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2a	4032–4203	30000	2003/12/06	6825	83	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2b	4032–4203	30000	2003/12/05	6825	84	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3a	4183–4395	23000	2003/12/06	6825	133	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3b	4183–4395	23000	2003/12/06	6825	137	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4340–4589	20000	2003/12/07	6825	139	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4340–4589	20000	2003/12/07	6825	127	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5a	4537–4761	23000	2003/12/08	6825	153	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5b	4537–4761	23000	2003/12/07	6825	146	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6a	6299–6691	17000	2003/11/12	6825	145	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6b	6299–6691	17000	2003/10/12	6825	138	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2021/01/02	2 × 1655	150	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –175
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2021/01/02	2 × 1725	90	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –175
PGMW 3061	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G130M</i>	FUV	1131–1429	18000	2023/04/29	2066		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G160M</i>	FUV	1418–1790	19000	2023/04/29	1996		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1a	3850–4050	22000	2003/12/05	6825	133.8	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1b	3850–4050	22000	2003/10/16	6825	122.3	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2a	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/06	6825	89.4	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2b	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/05	6825	108.4	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3a	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	172.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3b	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	182.7	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	189.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	172.7	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5a	4537–4761	23000	2003/12/08	6825	206.8	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5b	4537–4761	23000	2003/12/07	6825	187.7	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6a	6300–6690	17000	2003/11/12	6825	202.8	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6b	6300–6690	17000	2003/10/12	6825	176.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	9861	2009/12/25	4 × 300	70	Martayan, C.	0.8 × 11 / –67.8
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	18340	2009/12/25	2 × 600	70	Martayan, C.	0.8 × 11 / –67.8
PGMW 3100	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G130M</i>	FUV	1131–1428	12000–16000	2020/09/29	1990		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G160M</i>	FUV	1418–1790	13000–20000	2020/09/29	1968		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1a	3850–4050	22000	2003/12/05	6825	113	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1b	3850–4050	22000	2003/10/16	6825	104	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2a	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/06	6825	77	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2b	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/05	6825	99	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3a	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	169	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3b	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	146	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	158	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	159	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5a	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/08	6825	193	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5b	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/07	6825	176	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6a	6300–6690	17000	2003/11/12	6825	178	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6b	6300–6690	17000	2003/10/12	6825	172	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2020/12/15	950	143	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / 0
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2020/12/15	1020	101	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / 0
PGMW3120	<i>FUSE</i>	<i>FUV/MDRS</i>	FUV	904–1189	20000	2003/07/09	7354	7	Chu, You-Hua	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E140M</i>	FUV	1140–1735	45800	2000/04/14	8595		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.6
	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E230M</i>	NUV	1574–2382	30000	2017/05/28	3810		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2021/02/25	490	154	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –105
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2021/02/25	560	101	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –105

(1) Object; (2) telescope; (3) instrument/technique; (4) identification; (5) spectral range; (6) resolving power; (7) date of observation; (8) exposure time; (9) median signal-to-noise ratio; (10) principal investigator; (11) slit-size and position angle (N to E).

limit formerly suggested, being consistent with X-ray observations, however obtained with a different approach.

PGMW 3061. a.k.a. N11 31, is the earliest object in our sample, an O-type giant reclassified from O3 III(f*) (Parker et al. 1992) to ON2 III(f*) by Walborn et al. (2004); Evans et al.

(2006). According to our analysis of the GIRAFFE spectra, there is no evidence of binarity. We find that the He II λ 4686 profile of this star is variable in a period of 1 day (see Fig. D.6), that we attribute to wind variability. However, the difference in strength of this line is negligible and does not affect the determined $\dot{M}$.

Table A.2. (continue) Log of the spectroscopic observations used for the analysis of the ULLYSES targets in N11 B.

Object Name (1)	Telescope (2)	Instrument (3)	ID (4)	λ (Å) (5)	R (6)	Date (yy/mm/dd) (7)	Exp. t. (s) (8)	SNR (9)	P.I. (10)	slitsize / PA (arcsec / deg) (11)
PGMW 3168	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G130M</i>	FUV	1130–1428	12000–16000					
	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G160M</i>	FUV	1419–1790	19000	2023/02/10	1964		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/06	6825	113.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	191	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	178.8	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/08	6825	213.8	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/07	6825	195.7	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5	6300–6690	17000	2003/11/12	6825	182	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2020/12/20	2 × 1020	135	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / 0
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2020/12/20	2 × 950	90	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / 0
PGMW 3204	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E140M</i>	FUV	1141–1729	45800	2023/05/08	7768	20	Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2 / 104.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1a	3850–4050	22000	2003/12/05	6825	116.8	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1b	3850–4050	22000	2003/10/16	6825	108.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2a	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/06	6825	70.4	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2b	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/05	6825	83.4	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3a	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	142.7	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3b	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	146.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	152.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	139.7	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5a	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/08	6825	161.1	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5b	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/07	6825	146.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6a	6300–6690	17000	2003/11/12	6825	157.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>	<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6b	6300–6690	17000	2003/10/12	6825	135.2	Smartt, S.	D1.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2021/01/28	1200	134	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –50
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2021/01/28	1270	82	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –50
	PGMW 3223	<i>FUSE</i>	<i>FUV/MDRS</i>		904–1189	15000–20000	2002/09/23	7106		Roman-Duval, J.
<i>HST</i>		<i>STIS/E140M</i>	FUV	1140–1735	45800	2017/05/20	7768		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
<i>HST</i>		<i>STIS/E230M</i>	NUV	1574–2382	30000	2017/05/13	4970		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1a	3850–4050	22000	2003/12/05	6825	185	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	1b	3850–4050	22000	2003/10/16	6825	170	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2a	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/06	6825	131	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	2b	4030–4200	30000	2003/12/05	6825	131	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3a	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	244	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	3b	4180–4400	23000	2003/12/06	6825	231	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4a	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	223	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	4b	4340–4590	20000	2003/12/07	6825	251	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5a	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/08	6825	272	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	5b	4540–4760	23000	2003/12/07	6825	250	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6a	6300–6690	17000	2003/11/12	6825	253	Smartt, S.	D1.2
<i>ESO-VLT-U2</i>		<i>GIRAFFEMOS</i>	6b	6300–6690	17000	2003/10/12	6825	227	Smartt, S.	D1.2; 0
<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>		X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2020/12/13	540	153	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –45
<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2020/12/13	610	103	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –45	
Sk –69° 50	<i>FUSE</i>	<i>FUV/LWRS</i>		904–1189	15000–20000	2004/06/13	9263		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E140M</i>	FUV	1140–1735	45800	2011/10/11	2839		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2020/12/10	640	155	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –50
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2020/12/10	710	97	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –50
Sk –66° 171	<i>FUSE</i>	<i>FUV/LWRS</i>		904–1189	15000–20000	2005/04/08	1267		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E140M</i>	FUV	1140–1735	45800	2022/01/28	3191		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E230M</i>	NUV	1574–2382	30000	2022/01/28	1200		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2021/01/04	2 × 100	100	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –160
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2021/01/04	2 × 200	80	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –160
N11 046	<i>HST</i>	<i>COS/G130M</i>	FUV	1090–1240	12000–16000	2023/02/13	1568		Roman-Duval, J.	D2.5
	<i>HST</i>	<i>STIS/E140M</i>	FUV	1140–1735	45800	2023/03/14	7218		Roman-Duval, J.	0.2 × 0.2
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	UVB	2989–5560	6655	2021/01/02	1200	151	Vink, J. S.	0.8 × 11 / –40
	<i>ESO-VLT-U3</i>	X-shooter	VIS	5337–10200	11333	2021/01/02	1270	87	Vink, J. S.	0.7 × 11 / –40

Previously, Mokiem et al. (2007a) determined $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5.84$, $T_\star=45$ kK, $\log g=3.85$, and $\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1})=-5.41$. Later, Rivero González et al. (2012) determined $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5.9$, $T_\star=47.8$ kK, $\log g=3.95$, and $\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1})=-5.7$. Compared with the later study, we obtain $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5.6$, a lower value by 0.3 dex based on Gaia DR3 photometry (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2016, 2023) and UV spectra constraints for its luminosity and extinction; we also get $T_\star=42$ kK, $\log g=3.7$, and $\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1})=-6.0$, which are lower values from previously reported. The replicated observables with BONN-SAI were: $T_\star=41.3$ kK, $\log g=3.85$, $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5.65$, and $v \sin i=120$ km s⁻¹. The evolutionary mass is in agreement with the spectroscopic one. Additionally, N has to be increased by 5, C is reduced by 10, and Si by 4.

The $v \sin i$ is determined from the metal line in absorption N v $\lambda 4603.8$ (EW= 660 mÅ; SNR= 120) and N v $\lambda 4619.9$ (EW= 400 mÅ; SNR= 80). Using N v $\lambda 4603.8$, $v \sin i=133$ km s⁻¹

and $v_{\text{mac}}=82$ km s⁻¹ were obtained, while with N v $\lambda 4619.9$, $v \sin i=113$ km s⁻¹ and $v_{\text{mac}}=79.9$ km s⁻¹ were determined. The average of the two values, $v \sin i=120$ km s⁻¹ and $v_{\text{mac}}=80$ km s⁻¹, is reported for this star.

Nazé et al. (2014) reported a $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}})=-6.6$. We report the same value, independently reproducing the observations.

PGMW 3100. a.k.a. N11 38, is a mid O giant star, reclassified from O6.5 V(f) (Parker et al. 1992) to O5 III(f+) by Evans et al. (2006), and revised as O5 III(f) by PAC (priv. comm.). With GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra, we find evidence of v_{rad} variability, consistent with it being a binary SB1. The lines of H, He I and He II in the range of 3870–4040 Å and the H α window (6520–6590 Å) have to be shifted by the difference in radial velocity of 9 km s⁻¹. In the 4670–4730 Å range, this v_{rad} difference is 7 km s⁻¹ (see Fig. D.1).

Earlier, Mokiem et al. (2007a) determined $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5.69$, $T_\star=41.0$ kK, $\log g=3.72$ and $\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1})=-5.81$.

Table B.1. Photometric values used to construct the SEDs of the analyzed stars in N11 B.

Band	magnitude							
	PGMW 3223	PGMW 3053	PGMW 3061	PGMW 3168	PGMW 3100	PGMW 3204	PGMW 3058	PGMW 3120
U1	11.998±0.021 ^a	...	12.699±0.221 ^a	12.58 ^h	13.007±0.049 ^a	12.87 ^h	12.901±0.104 ^a	11.700±0.024 ^a
U2	12.87 ^h	...	13.16 ^h	...	12.89 ^h	...	13.18 ^h	...
B1	12.768±0.052 ^a	13.04 ^e	13.595±0.029 ^a	13.57 ^h	13.736±0.029 ^a	13.85 ^h	14.092±0.034 ^a	12.496±0.074 ^a
B2	12.83 ^h	...	13.67 ^h	...	13.81 ^h	...	14.18 ^h	...
V1	12.896±0.153 ^a	13.13 ^e	13.491±0.0501 ^a	13.68 ^h	13.648±0.029 ^a	14.02 ^h	14.089±0.031 ^a	12.466±0.124 ^a
V2	12.93 ^h	...	13.68 ^h	...	13.81 ^h	...	14.24 ^h	...
R	13.210±0.10 ^b	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
G2	12.9626±0.0032 ^c	13.0918±0.0004	13.6624±0.0003	13.6189±0.0003	13.7639±0.0003	13.9583±0.0008	14.2088±0.0003	12.8676±0.0046
Gbp	12.8016±0.0055 ^c	12.9587±0.0027	13.5410±0.0024	13.4892±0.0025	13.6969±0.0024	13.6853±0.0035	13.9913±0.0056	12.6421±0.0067
Grp	12.9646±0.0021 ^c	13.1378±0.0012	13.5529±0.0015	13.6293±0.0010	13.6891±0.0008	13.9264±0.0019	14.0966±0.0039	12.8296±0.0025
G3 ^{kl}	13.326458±0.003264	13.078708±0.002791	13.639601±0.002793	13.609666±0.002786	13.749496±0.002789	14.033206±0.003400	14.198952±0.002786	13.793874±0.023012
Gbp ^{kl}	12.840068±0.003135	13.017043±0.003038	13.586996±0.003147	13.549040±0.002942	13.739211±0.002949	13.771400±0.003161	14.087885±0.005192	12.694622±0.003200
Grp ^{kl}	12.978003±0.003947	13.167009±0.003868	13.571906±0.004226	13.663751±0.003856	13.704623±0.003812	13.975013±0.004363	14.158316±0.005903	12.860391±0.004241
I	12.663±0.125 ^a	...	13.405±0.069 ^a	...	13.547±0.063 ^a	...	13.991±0.074 ^a	12.464±0.163 ^a
J1	13.121±0.033 ^d	13.339±0.021 ^d	13.574±0.029 ^d	13.786±0.026 ^d	13.733±0.035 ^d	14.20 ⁱ	14.199±0.060 ^d	12.946±0.040 ^d
J2	13.17 ⁱ	...	13.71 ⁱ	13.81 ⁱ	13.75 ⁱ	...	14.70 ⁱ	13.08 ⁱ
H1	13.194±0.047 ^d	13.314±0.025 ^d	13.485±0.039 ^d	13.795±0.044 ^d	13.770±0.049 ^d	...	14.218±0.078 ^d	12.997±0.048 ^d
K1	13.186±0.048 ^d	13.428±0.045 ^d	13.523±0.048 ^d	13.734±0.048 ^d	...	14.19 ⁱ	14.152±0.089 ^d	13.022±0.052 ^d
K2	...	13.35 ⁱ	13.76 ⁱ	13.18 ⁱ	13.70 ⁱ	...	14.29 ⁱ	13.07 ⁱ

References: (a) Bonanos et al. (2009); (b) Zacharias et al. (2012); (c) Gaia Collaboration (2018); (d) Cutri et al. (2003); (e) Evans et al. (2006); (f) Walborn et al. (1995); (g) Penny & Gies (2009); (h) Parker et al. (1992); (i) Cioni et al. (2011); (k) Gaia Collaboration et al. (2016); (l) Gaia Collaboration et al. (2023).

Fig. C.1. PoWR model for the star PGMW 3058. The observed spectra is shown by a blue line and the model by a red dashed line. (1st panel) SED with photometric magnitudes (colour boxes). The UV spectra better constrain the $E(B - V)$ and L_* of the star (also indicated at the upper right, among other parameters); (2nd and 3rd panel) *HST/COS* UV spectra normalized to the continuum model. The terminal velocity (v_∞) is determined from the blue edge of the C iv line in absorption. N enhancement is determined with N iii at 1183 and 1185 Å, also considering these ions in the optical range, and C abundances by using C iii at 1175 and 1176 Å in the UV. ISM absorption features by the H Lyman lines were considered in our modeling. Interstellar (i.s.) atomic, molecular and metal lines in absorption are indicated. There is a gap of around 10 Å in the observations around 1280, and 1605 Å, where no key lines are present.

We obtain $\log(L_*/L_\odot) = 5.5$, a lower value by 0.2 dex, based on Gaia DR3 photometry (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2016, 2023); also a lower temperature ($T_* = 38$ kK), and a lower mass-loss rate ($\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.25$). The replicated observables with BONNSAI were: $T_* = 37$ kK, $\log g = 3.7$, $\log(L_*/L_\odot) = 5.5$, and $v \sin i = 110 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. BONNSAI assumes a lower T_* by 1 kK. The evolutionary mass is close to the spectroscopic one. It has a N enrichment by 3, and Si is reduced by 4.

The $v \sin i$ is determined from the observed metal line in absorption C iv $\lambda 5801$ (EW = 260 mÅ; SNR = 90), resulting in $v \sin i = 99 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 92 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. C iv $\lambda 5811$ is weaker

(EW = 200 mÅ; SNR = 110). From this line we obtain $v \sin i = 67 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 110 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

Nazé et al. (2014) reported a $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) = -8.86$. We report $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) = -6.8$, consistent with X-ray observations.

PGMW 3120a. This is a mid O dwarf O5.5V(f^*) star (Parker et al. 1992), revised without change by PAC (priv. comm.). PGMW 3120 is actually a cluster with at least three massive stars, as can be noted by eye in the *HST/ACS* image in Fig. 2. The slit apertures of X-shooter in the optical, and FUSE in the UV, include the three sources. This is not the case for the STIS/*HST* spectrum covering only PGMW 3120a. Also,

Fig. C.2. PoWR model for PGMW 3058. (*left*) Balmer lines present in the observed spectrum: $H\alpha$, $H\beta$, $H\gamma$, $H\delta$, He and H10–H17, in comparison with the final model of the star. The surface gravity ($\log g$) parameter of the star is determined from the wings of the H lines. In this particular case, $H\gamma$ is the optimal line to use, given it is not blended by other lines (e.g., $H\delta$). $H\alpha$ is considered to determine $\dot{M}$. The $H\alpha$ line is affected by a strong absorption, most likely of nebular origin. (*right*) The most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, in comparison with the final model of the star. The temperature (T_*) of the star is determined by modeling the He I–He II ratios (e.g., He I $\lambda 4471.5$, and He II $\lambda 4541.6$). Singlet lines of He I (1s2p P), at 4387.9 and 4921.9 Å, identified with blue labels were not used for diagnostic. Not photospheric lines are indicated with green labels. He II $\lambda 4686$ is crucial to determine $\dot{M}$. The observed spectra are shown by a blue line and the PoWR model by a red dashed line. The most important lines are identified.

Table E.1. Physical parameters obtained with PoWR for O-type stars of different sub-type in LMC.

ID	T_*	$\log g$	$\log(L_*/L_\odot)$	$\log \dot{M}$	v_∞	R_*	M_*	$\log Q_H$	$\log Q_{He I}$	$\log Q_{He II}$	$\log L_{mec}$	$\log(L_X/L_{bol})$	D_{mom}	
(1)	[kK]	[cm s^{-2}]	[$L_\odot$]	[$M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$]	[km s^{-1}]	[$R_\odot$]	[$M_\odot$]	[ph s^{-1}]	[ph s^{-1}]	[ph s^{-1}]	[$L_\odot$]	(14)	(15)	
Sk –66° 171	30.5±0.5	3.3±0.05	5.7±0.1	–6.0 ± 0.1	1750±50	25.4	43	49.1	47.3	38.5	41.6	2.4	–6.4	–2.5
Sk –69° 50	33.0±0.5	3.4±0.05	5.4±0.1	–6.3 ± 0.1	1750±50	15.4	19	49.0	47.7	38.6	41.1	2.8	–6.5	–2.0
N11-046	31.5±0.5	4.1±0.05	5.0±0.1	–7.8 ± 0.1	250±50	10.7	46	48.1	45.9	39.4	40.3	1×10 ^{–4}	–7.6	–4.8

(1) ID (Parker et al. 1992); (2) effective temperature (T_*); (3) surface gravity ($\log g$); (4) bolometric luminosity (L_*); (5) mass-loss rate ($\log \dot{M}$); (6) terminal wind velocity (v_∞); (7) stellar radius (R_*) via the Stefan-Boltzmann law; ionizing photons of (9) H (Q_H); (10) He I ($Q_{He I}$); (11) and He II ($Q_{He II}$); (12) mechanical luminosity; (13) X-ray to bolometric luminosity ratio ($\log(L_X/L_{bol})$); (14) modified wind momentum (D_{mom}).

the photometric magnitudes of these sources are presumably for the cluster. Gaia DR2 and DR3 values are displayed in the SED. One can note that the central V magnitude is not consistent with the blue and red arms, being an outlier. The Gaia DR2 values are consistent with each other. In the first panel of Fig. C.7, the SED of the source is shown. A luminosity of $\log(L_*/L_\odot) = 5.95$ to match the X-shooter spectra corresponds to the luminosity of the clustered stars. However, such luminosity would imply a spectroscopic mass of 160 $M_\odot$. Therefore, we performed photometry in the F220W image, using standard IRAF tasks, on the three sources that make up the cluster in

PGMW 3120. We found that the three objects, named here as: PGMW 3120a, PGMW 3120b and PGMW 312005c, have practically the same brightness (14.07, 14.07, and 14.09 mag, respectively). Given this, we can assume that one-third of the luminosity of the cluster corresponds to the luminosity of our star (PGMW 3120a), being $\log(L_*/L_\odot) = 5.5$. This luminosity would imply a lower spectroscopic mass (57 $M_\odot$). In the SED of Fig. C.7, it can also be noted that there is no need to multiply the level of the flux of the STIS spectrum by any factor. This is consistent with it being the spectrum from a single source. On the other hand, the FUSE spectrum is divided by 3, in order to be at

Fig. C.7. PoWR model for PGMW 3120. The observed spectra is shown by a blue line and the model by a red dashed line. (1st panel) SED with photometric magnitudes (colour boxes). (2nd panel) *FUSE*/MRDS UV spectra normalized to the continuum model; (3rd and 4th panel) *HST*/*STIS* UV spectra normalized to the continuum model. Particularly sensitive to X-rays are the N v $\lambda\lambda$ 1238.8, 1242.8 and O vi $\lambda\lambda$ 1031.9, 1037.6 features. Interstellar (i.s.) atomic, molecular and metal lines in absorption are indicated. The legend "fudge" means that the *FUSE* spectrum needed to be scaled (see text for details). There is a gap around 1420 Å, where no key lines are present.

Fig. C.8. PoWR model for PGMW 3120. (*left*) Balmer lines in the observed spectrum in comparison with the final model of the star. The $\log g$ is determined from the wings of the H lines. $H\alpha$ is considered to determine $\dot{M}$. The $H\alpha$ line is affected by an emission line, most likely of nebular origin. (*right*) The most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, in comparison with the final model of the star. The T_{eff} of the star is determined by modeling the He I-He II ratios. Not photospheric lines are indicated with green labels. He II λ 4686 is crucial to determine $\dot{M}$. The observed spectra are shown by a blue line and the PoWR model by a red dashed line. The most important lines are identified.

Fig. C.11. PoWR model for PGMW 3204. The observed spectra is shown by a blue line and the model by a red dashed line. (1st panel) SED with photometric magnitudes (colour boxes). The UV spectra better constrain the $E(B - V)$ and L_* ; (2nd and 3rd panel) HST/COS UV spectra normalized to the continuum model. Interstellar (i.s.) atomic, molecular and metal lines in absorption are indicated. There is a gap of around $10 \text{ \AA}$ in the observations around 1280, and 1605 $\text{\AA}$, where no key lines are present.

Fig. C.12. PoWR model for PGMW 3204. (left) Balmer lines in the observed spectrum in comparison with the final model of the star. The $\log g$ is determined from the wings of the H lines. $H\alpha$ is considered to determine $\dot{M}$. The $H\alpha$ line is affected by an emission line, most likely of nebular origin. (right) The most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, in comparison with the final model of the star. The T_* of the star is determined by modeling the He I-He II ratios. Not photospheric lines are indicated with green labels. He II $\lambda 4686$ is crucial to determine $\dot{M}$. The observed spectra are shown by a blue line and the PoWR model by a red dashed line. The most important lines are identified.

Fig. C.15. PoWR model for Sk -69° 50. The observed spectra is shown by a blue line and the model by a red dashed line. (1st panel) SED with photometric magnitudes (colour boxes). (2nd panel) *FUSE*/MRDS UV spectra; and (3rd and 4th panel) *HST*/*STIS* UV spectra normalized to the continuum model. Particularly sensitive to X-rays are the N V $\lambda\lambda$ 1238.8, 1242.8 and O VI $\lambda\lambda$ 1031.9, 1037.6 features. Interstellar (i.s.) atomic, molecular and metal lines in absorption are indicated.

Fig. C.16. PoWR model for Sk -69° 50. (*left*) Balmer lines in the observed spectrum in comparison with the final model of the star. The $\log g$ is determined from the wings of the H lines. $H\alpha$ is considered to determine $\dot{M}$. The $H\alpha$ line is affected by an emission line, most likely of nebular origin. (*right*) The most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, in comparison with the final model of the star. The T_* of the star is determined by modeling the He I-He II ratios. Not photospheric lines are indicated with green labels. He II λ 4686 is crucial to determine $\dot{M}$. The observed spectra are shown by a blue line and the PoWR model by a red dashed line. The most important lines are identified.

Fig. C.17. PoWR model for Sk -66° 171. The observed spectra is shown by a blue line and the model by a red dashed line. (1st panel) SED with photometric magnitudes (colour boxes). (2nd panel) *FUSE*/*MRDS* UV spectra; and (3rd and 4th panel) *HST*/*STIS* UV spectra normalized to the continuum model. Particularly sensitive to X-rays are the N v $\lambda\lambda 1238.8, 1242.8$ and O vi $\lambda\lambda 1031.9, 1037.6$ features. Interstellar (i.s.) atomic, molecular and metal lines in absorption are indicated.

Fig. C.18. PoWR model for Sk -66° 171. (left) Balmer lines in the observed spectrum in comparison with the final model of the star. The $\log g$ is determined from the wings of the H lines. $H\alpha$ is considered to determine $\dot{M}$. The $H\alpha$ line is affected by an emission line, most likely of nebular origin. (right) The most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, in comparison with the final model of the star. The T_* of the star is determined by modeling the He I-He II ratios. Not photospheric lines are indicated with green labels. He II $\lambda 4686$ is crucial to determine $\dot{M}$. The observed spectra are shown by a blue line and the PoWR model by a red dashed line. The most important lines are identified.

Fig. C.19. PoWR model for N11 046. The observed spectra is shown by a blue line and the model by a red dashed line. (1st panel) SED with photometric magnitudes (colour boxes). (2nd panel) *HST/COS* UV spectra; and (3rd and 4th panel) *HST/STIS* UV spectra normalized to the continuum model. Particularly sensitive to X-rays are the N V $\lambda\lambda$ 1238.8, 1242.8 and O V $\lambda\lambda$ 1031.9, 1037.6 features. Interstellar (i.s.) atomic, molecular and metal lines in absorption are indicated. There is a gap around 1090 Å, where no key lines are present.

Fig. C.20. PoWR model for N11 046. (*left*) Balmer lines in the observed spectrum in comparison with the final model of the star. The $\log g$ is determined from the wings of the H lines. $H\alpha$ is considered to determine $\dot{M}$. The $H\alpha$ line is affected by an emission line, most likely of nebular origin. (*right*) The most important He I and He II lines, as well as some metals, in comparison with the final model of the star. The T_* of the star is determined by modeling the He I-He II ratios. Not photospheric lines are indicated with green labels. He II λ 4686 is crucial to determine $\dot{M}$. The observed spectra are shown by a blue line and the PoWR model by a red dashed line. The most important lines are identified.

Fig. D.2. PGMW 3223 GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra to check for binary: radial velocity or line profile difference. Some of the lines have been shifted by the difference in radial velocity, 20 – 30 km s⁻¹ (green line), to compare their line profiles.

Fig. D.3. PGMW 3204 GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra to check for binary: radial velocity or line profile difference. No evidence for binary component in the Balmer nor He lines.

Fig. D.4. PGMW 3204 GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra to check for binary: radial velocity or line profile difference. No evidence for binary component in the Balmer nor He lines.

Fig. D.5. PGMW 3053 GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra to check for binary: radial velocity or line profile difference. No evidence for binary component in the Balmer nor He lines. Only H α displays a variable profile, probably because of wind variability.

Fig. D.6. PGMW 3061 GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra to check for binary. Only He II $\lambda 4686$ displays a variable profile, probably because of wind variability.

The $\dot{M}$ that we find ($\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.75$) is lower than the one reported by Mokiem et al. (2007a). The replicated observables with BONNSAI were: $T_{\star} = 33.2$ kK, $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.3$, $\log g = 3.6$, and $v \sin i = 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. A higher value by 0.1 dex is assumed for $\log g$, affecting the obtained M_{ev} . We find that N is increased by a factor of 3, C by 2, and Si reduced by 4.

The $v \sin i$ is determined from the observed metal line in absorption Si IV $\lambda 4088.9$ (EW = 210 mÅ; SNR = 170), resulting in $v \sin i = 55 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 89 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Using an-

other metal line, N III $\lambda 4515$ (EW = 44 mÅ; SNR = 314), we obtain a similar value for $v \sin i = 67 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, however different for $v_{\text{mac}} = 26 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. We prioritize the values obtained with Si IV $\lambda 4088.9$, given its EW is stronger. This star has the slowest $v \sin i$ and the lowest $T_{\star}$ of the analyzed targets. It is also among the objects with the lowest $\log g$, and therefore with the lowest mass, $M_{\text{spec}} = 27 M_{\odot}$ of the analyzed stars.

Nazé et al. (2014) reported a $\log(L_{\text{X}}/L_{\text{bol}}) < -6.8$ for this object. We report $\log(L_{\text{X}}/L_{\text{bol}}) = -7.0$, a value below the upper limit suggested, consistent with previous observations.

PGMW 3204. a.k.a. N11 48, is a mid O dwarf star, reclassified from O6-O7 V (Parker et al. 1992) to O6.5 V by Evans et al. (2006), and revised as O6 Vz(f) by PAC (priv. comm.). Formerly, Mokiem et al. (2007a) determined $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.38$, $T_{\star} = 40.7$ kK, $\log g = 4.19$ and $\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.78$. We obtain the same $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot})$, a higher temperature ($T_{\star} = 42.0$ kK) and surface gravity ($\log g = 4.3$), the highest of the sample, with a mass of $66 M_{\odot}$ and $\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.6$. The replicated observables with BONNSAI were: $T_{\star} = 42.7$ kK, $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.3$, $\log g = 4.17$, and $v \sin i = 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Lower values by 0.1 dex are assumed for $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot})$ and $\log g$, affecting the obtained M_{ev} , which is lower than M_{spec} almost by half. It has a N enrichment by 3, C is reduced by 10, O by 4 and Si by 4.

A $v \sin i = 58 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 97 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is determined from the C IV $\lambda 5801$ (EW = 140 mÅ; SNR = 130).

Nazé et al. (2014) reported a $\log(L_{\text{X}}/L_{\text{bol}}) = -6.6$. We report $\log(L_{\text{X}}/L_{\text{bol}}) = -6.4$, the highest among the analyzed targets. According to its GIRAFFE spectra (see Fig. D.3 and D.4) there is no conclusive evidence of binary.

PGMW 3223. a.k.a. N11 13, is a late O dwarf star, among the brightest objects ($V = 12.9$ mag) in N11 B, reclassified from O8.5 IV (Parker et al. 1992) to O8 V by Evans et al. (2006), and revised as O8 Vz by PAC (priv. comm.). According to our analysis of the GIRAFFE multi-epoch spectra, we confirm binary SB1 features, also noted by Evans et al. (2006). The lines of H, He I and He II in the range of 3870 – 4040 Å and the H α window (6520 – 6590 Å) have to be shifted by the difference in radial velocity of 30 km s^{-1} . In the 4670 – 4730 Å range, this v_{rad} difference is 20 km s^{-1} (see Fig. D.2).

Previously, Serebriakova et al. (2023) reports $T_{\star} = 33.8$ kK and $\log g = 3.6$. We obtain $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.5$, $T_{\star} = 34.0$ kK, $\log g = 3.9$, and $\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.7$. The observables with BONNSAI were: $T_{\star} = 35.1$ kK, $\log g = 3.58$, $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.4$, and $v \sin i = 110 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The $\log g$ is lower by 0.27 dex, affecting the obtained M_{ev} , which is lower than M_{spec} by half.

The $v \sin i$ of this object is determined from the metal line in absorption O III $\lambda 5592.3$ (EW = 215 mÅ; SNR = 75), resulting in $v \sin i = 108 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $v_{\text{mac}} = 93 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

Nazé et al. (2014) reported $\log(L_{\text{X}}/L_{\text{bol}}) < -6.9$. We report $\log(L_{\text{X}}/L_{\text{bol}}) = -7.1$, consistent with the predicted value.

Additional objects. In order to quantify the total ionizing feedback of the O-type stars in N11 B, three additional objects in the LMC were analyzed in this work (see Sec. 4.6). We introduce them here so that we can use additional stellar and wind parameters for comparison with our objects in N11 B. We report their main parameters at the Appendix (see Tables E.1, E.2, E.3), as well as their respective modeling.

Sk -66° 171. For this late O-type supergiant, classified as O9 Ia (Fitzpatrick 1988), Martins et al. (2024) reported $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) = 5.7$, $T_{\star} = 30$ kK, and $\log g = 3.0$. We obtain consistent values for $\log(L_{\star}/L_{\odot}) (= 5.7)$, and $T_{\star} = 30.5$ kK, but a higher $\log g (= 3.3)$. We also determine $\log(\dot{M}/M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = -6.0$.

Sk -69° 50. For this mid-O-type supergiant, classified as O7(n)(f)p (Walborn et al. 2010), and revised as O7I(n)(f)p by PAC (priv. comm.), Martins et al. (2024) reported $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5.45$, $T_\star=35.0$ kK and $\log g=3.4$. We obtain a close value for $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)(=5.4)$, a lower $T_\star(=33$ kK), and the same $\log g(=3.4)$. We also determine $\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1})=-6.3$.

[ELS2006] N11 046. For this late-O-type dwarf, classified as O9.5 V (Evans et al. 2006), and revised as O9.7 III by PAC (priv. comm.), we report $\log(L_\star/L_\odot)=5$, $T_\star=31.5$ kK, $\log g=4.1$ and $\log(\dot{M}/M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1})=-7.8$.